

POSSIBLE ANTITUBERCULOUS COMPOUNDS. PART VIII. PREPARATION OF DIPHENYLAMINE-4-ARYL- OR -ALKYL-AMIDINES,

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With a view to increasing the basic strength and surface area of *N*-4-diphenylamidines, compounds of known antitubercular activity, several diphenylamine-4-aryl- or -alkyl-amidines have been prepared.

In the present communication we have tried to increase the basicity and surface area of *N*-4-diphenylamidines by introducing a secondary nitrogen atom between the two benzene rings of diphenyl moiety and then preparing several new amidines from 4-aminodiphenylamine by adopting the usual method of Oxley and Short (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 147).

The 4-aminodiphenylamine was converted into 4-diphenylamine-ammonium benzenesulphonate by adopting the method of Bauer and Cymerman (*ibid.*, 1950, 1826). That the monosulphonate of 4-aminodiphenylamine was formed and not the disulphonate, was confirmed by the sulphur as well as nitrogen estimations. It was also envisaged that the addition of benzenesulphonic acid took place on the primary amino group and not on the secondary amino group of 4-aminodiphenylamine. This was confirmed by the failure of the dye test when applied to the 4-diphenylamine-ammonium benzenesulphonate.

The benzenesulphonate on fusing with an excess of benzo-, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-tolyl-, α - and β -naphtho-, butyro-, valero-, capro^o- and caproⁱ-nitriles at 230-40° yielded appropriate amidine-benzenesulphonates after repeated trituration with acetone or ether.

The amidine-benzenesulphonates were then converted into amidines by the usual method of basification and isolation. The latter were recrystallised either from chloroform-petroleum ether or from ethanol.

[R=Ph, tolyl (*o*-, *m*- & *p*-), naphthyl (α & β), C₃H₇, C₄H₉, C₅H₁₁ⁱ and C₆H₁₁ⁿ]

The antitubercular activity of the amidines will be reported later on.

EXPERIMENTAL

(I). *4-Diphenylamine-ammonium Benzenesulphonate* (A).—4-Aminodiphenylamine (5.2g.) was suspended in dry ether (20 c.c.) and benzenesulphonic acid (6.0 g.), dissolved in methanol, was added to it dropwise under stirring. A light green solid separated out. It was filtered, dried and

recrystallised from hot water as a green amorphous powder, m.p. 204-205°, yield 9.0 g. (93%). (Found : N, 7.72 ; S, 8.88. $C_{18}H_{18}O_3N_2S$ requires N, 8.18 ; S, 9.35%).

TABLE I

Compounds. (R =)	M.P.	% Yield.	Recrystallised from.	Appearance (Powder).
Ph	163°	92	Ether	Brown
<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	245°	90	Acetone	„
<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	145°	90	Ethanol	Dark brown
<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	190	50	Acetone	Brown
<i>α</i> -C ₁₀ H ₇	115° (decomp.)	30	Ethanol	Black
<i>β</i> -C ₁₀ H ₇	176-77	76	Ether	Dark brown
C ₃ H ₇	183°	85	Acetone	Grey
C ₄ H ₉	146-47	86	Ether	Brown
C ₆ H ₁₁ ⁿ	167	77	Do	Dark grey
C ₆ H ₁₁ ^t	210°	16	Acetone	Dark brown

(II). *Diphenylamine-4-alkyl- or aryl-amidines*.—The compound (A) was converted into different amidine-benzenesulphonates and subsequently to corresponding free amidines, by adopting the usual method of their formation (Misra *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 695 ; 1959, 36, 270).

TABLE II

Amidine (R=).	M.P.	% Yield.	Appearance (Powder).	Formula	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.
Ph	85°	87	Green	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃	14.14	14.63
<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	110°	75	Dark grey	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃	14.35	13.95
<i>m</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	132-33°	83	Brown	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃	14.20	13.95
<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃	102°	68	Light grey	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃	14.30	13.95
<i>α</i> -C ₁₀ H ₇	170°	61	Black	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₃	12.10	12.46
<i>β</i> -C ₁₀ H ₇	137-38°	66	Grey	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₃	12.77	12.46
C ₃ H ₇	140°	5	Black	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃	16.24	16.60
C ₄ H ₉	161-162	7	Black	C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₃	16.00	15.70
C ₆ H ₁₁ ⁿ	90°	6	Black	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ N ₃	14.60	14.90
C ₆ H ₁₁ ^t	157-58°	46	Brown	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ N ₃	14.45	14.90

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